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Provision of the individual's psychological security: The possibility of formation and correction

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Abstract--The aim of the study the need for security has always been one of the most important human challenges at any age. People have always suffered and had to defend themselves against a variety of threats. Currently, the number of dangers affecting their mental health and emotional well-being is growing rapidly. In today's world, people are becoming more and more psychologically vulnerable. The speed of general social changes and strong information pressure nowadays exceed personal opportunities for adaptability. Under such conditions, everyday life becomes more dangerous, more risky for physical and mental health. The present academic paper is devoted to studying the mechanisms of formation of the individual's psychological security, which is of significant practical importance in the conditions of political and social-economic instability of the modern society in the world. The scientific article analyses the process of acquiring psychological security, the starting point of which is the

construction of a model of the world in the coordinates of the vital meanings of the individual, structuring it in a certain way according to the security level. The purpose of the academic paper lies in analysing the features of the process of forming and correcting the psychological security of the individual. Methodology. The data from international studies, scientific publications and survey results of residents of the temporarily occupied territories of Ukraine have been used in the research. Results. With the aid of the questionnaire, the values of the components of the individual's psychological security have been revealed from the point of view of the inhabitants of the territories where active hostilities have been carried out, which is of particular importance for the formation of personality-oriented mechanisms of psychological work with such categories of people. According to the results of the survey conducted, the priorities of correcting the level of psychological security include forecasting life prospects and developing skills to relieve emotional stress in order to quickly and deeply recover.

Keywords---psychological security, subjective and objective content of psychological security, correction, mental health, psychological protection.

Introduction

The relevance of the issue raised in the present academic paper lies in the fact that the psychological security of the individual is a necessary condition for his development in the process of life, the prevention of psychosomatic disorders and the implementation of personal potential. In addition, a psychologically protected person is the one who “builds his own life in the context of unity with the society, nature, the universe, delivers on the capabilities, ideals and aspirations through a system of meaningful life regulation, is ready to ensure his own safety and health through the transformation of dangers into a factor of his own development” (Hajek & König, 2018).

The urgency of the issue of people's psychological security in our difficult times arises due to the unpredictable consequences of unilateral, often humanistic, manifestations of scientific and technological progress, information overload of human living space, numerous natural, man-made and social shocks that are becoming increasingly complex.

The need for psychological security has always been and is one of the most important human challenges. People have always suffered and had to defend themselves against various threats and dangers. However, while in the past and in partly modern times, their physical health, well-being and livelihoods have been threatened mostly in theory, currently, the number of threats and dangers affecting their mental health and psychological well-being is growing rapidly (Mauramo, Lahti, Lallukka & Lahelma et al., 2019).

The problem of psychological security of the individual is relevant in both professional and personal relationships. On the one hand, professional activity can be a source of satisfaction, increasing self-esteem, expanding social contacts, intellectual and emotional mood; in this case, a person effectively performs his professional duties and continues to grow professionally. However, on the other hand, it is a cause of stress and psychological tension.

Ensuring the safety of people is one of the most difficult and popular issues nowadays. The imaginary simplicity of everyday understanding of this issue should not be misleading. The issue of security concerns the fundamental aspects of human existence; it has an ideological, scientific-theoretical and applied level of consideration.

Literature Review

Currently, there is no single interpretation of the term “psychological security”. Academic dictionaries in English, French and German reflect the “personal security” concept, which is associated with the state, feelings, experiences of a person regarding his current situation and future prospects. The issue of understanding the psychological security of the individual, refracted through the prism of the “environmental approach”, leads to the crowding theory (stress caused by subjective feelings of discomfort in space, the environment in which a person is). Crowding was actively studied by Nagasu, M., Kogi, K. & Yamamoto, I. (Nagasu, Kogi & Yamamoto, 2019).

A number of studies are devoted to the phenomenon of psychological security, in which attempts are made to look at the conditions of its provision from different standpoints. Analysing the meaning of the term “security”, the researchers come to the conclusion that this term is less identified with the “absence of threats” in the public consciousness, and more with the state, feelings and experiences of people. (Shinkar, 2021). In general, the term “security” is associated with a state and a sense of security, fearlessness or carefreeness, trust, stability. Different concepts of security focus primarily on human feelings and experiences in the current situation and future prospects. Mental security is defined as a state of public consciousness in which the society as a whole and each individual perceives the current state of reality and life as appropriate and reliable, considering that there are real opportunities to meet the natural and social needs of citizens today and implement confidence in the future (Duchaine, Ndjaboué, Levesque & Vézina, et al., 2017).

Psychological security of the individual is a necessary condition for the development of its functional abilities, prevention of psychosomatic disorders and personal fulfilment. Along with this, a person who has achieved psychological security is a person who “moulds his own life in the context of unity with the society, nature, the universe, fulfils his own capabilities, ideals and aspirations through the created system of semantic regulation of life, and is ready to ensure the safety and strengthening of his own health, turning danger into a factor of his own development” (Afolabi & Baloguna, 2017).

In studies on the issue of self-regulation of human volitional activity Slyusarevskyy, M. has shown that the regulation of activity occurs not only on the basis of a causal relationship, but has a complex synthetic configuration. Self-regulation in the investigations of this scholar is defined as a type of internal state, traits or abilities that are genetically inherited and are self-discovering through self-reflection (Slyusarevskyy, 2020).

Andrushko, Ja, who studied the concept of learning in psychology, has revealed that the body acts as a holistic system; consequently, the state of psychological security can be considered as an independent goal, the end result of the subject and as a means to achieve another goal (Andrushko, 2017). All theoretical concepts studying psychological security can be divided into five main groups as follows:

- Theories explaining the phenomenon of overload - an excess of information or the need to make many decisions in a short period of time. The perception of stress depends on the individual level of adaptation: the more deviations from the level of adaptation, the greater the stress is.
- Stress is connected with reduced freedom to make decisions and act. These experiences are to a large extent determined by cultural norms, physical and psychological distance accepted in the community.
- The environmental approach developed by R. Barker offers the concept of underpopulation and overpopulation. Overcrowding, when there are fewer roles than people, creates tension. The presence of other people is perceived negatively.
- Attribution theories suggest that it is important how a person explains his irritation; he attributes the cause of stress to other people or circumstances.
- The studies of the fifth group use the concept of locus of control (individual strategy). The cause of stress is the loss of control over the environment. The person feels that he cannot change the situation. The place of control determines the attitude to a stressful situation (Cjuman & Nagula, 2018).

In psychology, the issue of psychological protection is often considered. Pustovojt, M. perceives the psychological security of a person as “a certain protection of consciousness from influences that, contrary to his will and desire, can change mental states, psychological features and behaviour that can dramatically affect a person until he changes his life path”. The scientist separates the security of the human psyche from the manipulation of his consciousness. In most cases, manipulation is understood as a mental influence that affects a person’s consciousness against his will (Pustovojt, 2017).

Wang, J., Long R., Chen H., & Li Q. consider the psychological security of the individual, which is determined by the level of subjectivity (perceptual, cognitive, emotional processes) and objective factors - the level of development of the environment (Wang, Long, Chen, & Li, 2019). Pustovojt, M. defines the security of the individual as “the formation of a set of legal and moral norms, social institutions and organizations that allow him to develop and implement socially significant skills and needs without feeling the opposition of the state and the society” (Pustovojt, 2017).

Slyusarevskyy, M. considers the structure of security psychology in two aspects, namely: psychological security of the environment and psychological security of the individual. The psychological safety of the environment in the social aspect is defined as the state of the environment, free from psychological violence in the interaction of people, which contributes to the satisfaction of basic needs in personal communication, creating the reference value of the environment and, accordingly, providing psychological protection. At the same time, the personality manifests himself in the ability to maintain resistance to destructive internal and external influences in an environment with certain parameters, including traumatic influences (Slyusarevskyy, 2020).

Abbas J., Aqeel M. & Abbas J., studying the psychological security of the environment, propose to classify all dangers and threats according to the purpose, process and result of the impact, reflection, perception, level of consciousness, impact possibilities, structural organization, the ability of individuals to counter these threats (Abbas, Aqeel & Abbas, 2019).

The concept of psychological security is also used in connection with the professional activities of people. The scientific substantiation of this concept is contained in the research work of Cjuman, T. & Nagula, O., who consider the issue of psychological safety as a prevention of accidents at work, developed in the framework of industrial psychology. It is important to emphasize that the authors propose to consider the psychology of security “not as a branch of industrial psychology, but as a separate branch of psychological science that studies the psychological aspect of security at various jobs”. They believe that the psychology of security affects such areas of psychological science as: psychology of psychology, engineering psychology, military psychology, aerospace psychology, sports psychology, medical psychology, forensic psychology. They argue that “there is a general psychological problem - the study of the process of formation of human life in conditions of psychological danger and the search for ways to ensure it, in the centre of which there is a person - the subject of activity, and not the means of production” (Cjuman. & Nagula, 2018).

De la Fuente, Peralta-Sánchez, Martínez-Vicente, Sander, Garzón-Umerenkova & Zapata define security psychology as a field of psychology: “Psychology of safety is a field of psychological science that studies the psychological causes of accidents occurring during work and other activities and suggests ways in which psychology can be used to improve safety” (De la Fuente, Peralta-Sánchez, Martínez-Vicente, Sander, Garzón-Umerenkova & Zapata, 2020). Therefore, we have two psychological definitions: psychological security as the safety of the environment and psychological security as an individual psychological quality of a person, which involves the ability to protect against threats and dangers.

The psychological security of a person is nothing other than the protection of his psyche from destructive external and internal influences. The emphasis on the fact that destructive influences can be both external and internal, which are made by almost all authors dealing with psychological security, is quite appropriate. Threats and dangers can really fall on a person from the outside, stemming from the depths of his own psyche, a deformed life (in the form of inspired or self-suggested fear, unfounded social fears, prejudices, too harsh distortions of reality,

other protective factors, etc.). Psychology of safety studies the various types of human activity that are associated with danger. The subjects of research in this area are as follows: mental processes generated by activities affecting their safety; mental states of a person affecting the safety of his activities; personality traits affecting the safety of activities.

According to the viewpoint of Berg N., Kiviruusu O. & Lintonen T., the threat to the psychological security of the subject of professional activity is understood as a set of obstacles in the process of meeting the needs of the subject in activities, the uniqueness of which is based on numerous factors of both external and internal environment of the subject's activity (Berg, Kiviruusu & Lintonen, 2019). The issue of psychological security of the individual is of particular importance in connection with solving problems in order to determine the optimal workload of workers whose professional activities are connected with special and extreme conditions, identifying human resources and ergonomic optimization of human-professional interaction.

By the way, the observations of Slyusarevskyy, M. are interesting and well-founded from the point of view of psychological security. The scholar states that we have two types of psychological security, namely: psychological security as environmental security and psychological security as an individual psychological quality of a person, which involves the ability to defend oneself against threats and dangers. The formation of psychological security of the individual includes several successive stages, the first of which lies in obtaining the information about the level of security or danger to the human environment that arises in the process of building a subjective worldview. It is the phenomena of the surrounding reality are in some way structured by a person according to his values and needs and are encoded in the individual consciousness as safe or dangerous ones. Accordingly, a person has a basic sense of security or danger of his own existence in the environment, which, accordingly, determines the direction of his further activities: with a sense of security, a person experiences positive emotions such as happiness, inspiration, desire to interact with others; however, when a person experiences some danger, he may show a tendency to self-isolation and alienation, focusing on negative feelings of fear and danger (Slyusarevskyy, 2020).

According to the viewpoint of Notten N., Grunow D. & Verbakel E., psychological security of the individual is formed from the interaction of a set of mental and perceptual processes that have certain individual features and, accordingly, involve the coordination of individual abilities in the context of environmental requirements (Notten, Grunow & Verbakel, 2017). Therefore, the formation of psychological security of the individual is a set of interrelated processes of perception and evaluation of the environment, as well as "scanning" and identifying dangers from the standpoint of the individual.

The aim of the research

The purpose of the research lies in analysing the features and composition of the psychological security of the inhabitants of the temporarily occupied territories of Ukraine, the most effective areas of its formation and correction.

Materials and Methods

The study of the process of formation and correction of the individual's psychological security was carried out by interviewing residents of the temporarily occupied territories of Ukraine (Kyiv, Kharkiv, Cherkasy, Donetsk and Luhansk regions) by psychotherapists of state medical institutions in March 2021 and in March 2022, that is, one year prior to and 30 days after the beginning of the full-scale invasion of the Russian Federation into the territory of Ukraine. The survey involved 212 people aged 35-45, including 106 women and 106 men. In particular, the survey questionnaire included questions concerning as follows:

- assessments of the general level of psychological security;
- assessment of the level of individual components of psychological well-being;
- identification of the most effective directions of correction of personal psychological safety from the point of view of the survey participants.

The residents were asked to determine the importance of the survey's certain categories in the percentage from 0% to 100%, after which the average score for the group was calculated.

Results and Discussion

The conducted survey has made it possible to assess the state of psychological security of the respondents, in particular, their ability to show resilience in an environment with certain parameters, including psycho-traumatic events. According to the results of the assessment, one of the following psychological security levels of the respondents was determined, as follows:

- a state of complete psychological security (resistance of the individual to external and internal actions);
- lack of psychological security (tendency to disrupt the functioning of the person, manifested in behaviour and activities);
- a state of "hidden" psychological insecurity (as the possibility of transition to the first and second states under the influence of external and internal factors (Figure 1.)

Figure 1. Assessment of the general state of respondents' psychological security, %

As it can be seen from the above data, in general, the number of respondents whose state of psychological safety was assessed by psychotherapists as "complete psychological safety" decreased from 17% to 2%; the number of respondents who had "hidden" psychological insecurity decreased from 69% to 25%; and the number of those whose condition was rated as "lack of psychological security" increased from 14% to 73%. Studying the components of psychological security of respondents, the following results were obtained in the course of the research (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Assessment of components of respondents' psychological security, %

The assessment was carried out as a percentage of the most positive result, where 100% is the maximum possible degree of the indicator development. As it can be seen from Figure 2, after a full-scale military invasion, on average, respondents' physical health decreased slightly; their level of morale decreased significantly (from 49% to 21%); and their level of inner comfort dropped from 39% to 3%. At the same time, an increase in the motivational and value components of psychological security is observed. The research has revealed that in order to maintain a person's personal psychological security, the following aspects are of particular importance for respondents, namely:

- democratization of public life and the formation of the civil society;
- the sequence of solving social-psychological problems within the framework of the cultural and historical cycle;
- public confidence in various social institutions;
- role interaction and productivity in groups;
- adjustment of social tensions;
- establishment of social dialogues in the society in order to rationally regulate social relations;
- overcoming the psychotraumatic consequences of military conflict (Figure 3).

Figure 3. The effectiveness of the formation and correction of psychological security of the individual, %

In the course of the research, the respondents were asked to take a course of online classes in order to increase the level of personal psychological security and to assess the effectiveness and relevance of the target areas of this course (Figure 4).

Figure 4. The relevance of the target areas of correction of the individual's psychological security, %

As the result of the survey has shown, from the point of view of respondents, the most important steps for the correction of the level of psychological security are the forecasting of life prospects and the development of skills to relieve emotional stress in order to quickly and deeply recover. Thus, Viertiö S., Kiviruusu O., Piirtola M. & Kaprio J. studying the methods of psychological influence on people, consider the psychological security as “the state of the information environment and living conditions of a particular person, group, society as a whole, which does not contribute to the integrity, adaptability and development of social actors (individual, group, society as a whole)” (Viertiö, Kiviruusu, Piirtola & Kaprio, 2021).

Geisler M., Berthelsen H. & Hakanen J. define the social aspects of psychological security; they propose to consider the social-psychological security as a state of dynamic balance between the internal potential of the subject and external conditions due to the presence of relationships that bring satisfaction and security (without deformations, injuries and difficulties), as well as tolerance in relationships that allows fulfilling the spiritual and mental potential of the subject in the life process in order to preserve its integrity (Geisler, Berthelsen & Hakanen, 2019).

Andrushko Ja., in his scientific works, tries to analyse the protective mechanism of the person in terms of the possibility of achieving psychological security, based on the abilities of the subject, which forms a sense of overcoming certain obstacles in life. The scholar proposes to consider the issues of psychological security from the point of view of personal growth and development, in the framework of which it is necessary to analyse the conditions, under which a person can turn problems into tasks, and then into opportunities for self-development. If a person perceives his obstacles as opportunities, that is, in the event of a change in the subjective attitude towards them, he shifts the emphasis

from the personal meaning of the problem to the personal meaning of its solution (Andrushko, 2017).

Pustovojt M. described the mechanism of revealing the potential of psychological security of the individual as a change in the structure of alternatives in the context of analysing the problem of choice (Pustovojt, 2017). There are two directions in the study of psychological security: objective and subjective. Object orientation in the study of psychological security of a person involves the consideration of the individual as an object of psychological security in certain conditions. The subjective direction involves understanding a person as an active subject of ensuring one's own psychological security: the study of the psychological aspects of the formation of the individual's safe behaviour at different stages of his life.

As it has been rightly noted by Hiesinger K. & Tophoven S., numerous scientists identify the factors of psychological security of the individual as follows: factors of objective order (ensuring the psychological security of the person at the individual level, which depend on the cultural and historical development of the society); factors of objective-subjective order (determine the psychological security of the individual as a social person): the personal ability of the individual to adapt within the limits of socially accepted moral norms, the ability to understand and accept others, to be socially significant among others, to be accepted by others; factors of subjective order (provide psychological security of the individual, form the motivational and semantic attitudes of the individual) (Hiesinger & Tophoven, 2019). In particular, scholars emphasize that the procedural self-sufficiency of the subject in extreme situations should be based on achieving mental control of exogenous and endogenous parameters and maintaining a dynamic balance with the environment at the somatic, energy and information levels, ensuring security vital to achieving goals.

According to the viewpoint of Hiilamo A., Shiri R., Kouvonen A. & Mänty M. et al., psychological security is formed in the process of complex interaction of mental and perceptual processes, the result of which is a certain "scanning" of the world in order to determine the degree of its safety for a person. The formation of psychological security occurs in the process of categorizing the environment, creating an individual model of the world, defined by the person in the dimensions of security / danger in the coordinates of his life feelings and values, which are relevant "markers" of security or danger. Accepting the existence of opposites of security / danger in life helps to increase the degree of human adaptation to threats and enhances his potential for development and self-fulfilment (Hiilamo, Shiri, Kouvonen & Mänty, 2019).

Personal security strategies can be productive to varying degrees, depending on the maturity and autonomy of the individual, his ability to implement his own life scenario in accordance with his own values and goals. Effective practical means of improving the psychological security of the individual are social-psychological classes aimed at increasing personal subjectivity, skills of perception and communication, self-acceptance, self-regulation and life satisfaction, as well as risk tolerance as a challenge to conquer new personal heights.

Conclusions

Therefore, the psychological security of the individual (in a broad sense) includes as follows:

- firstly, the appropriate level of theoretical and practical training of the individual, through which the protection and implementation of his vital interests and harmonious development are achieved, regardless of the information capabilities of the individual;
- secondly, the ability to create conditions for the harmonious development and satisfaction of individual needs regardless of the presence of information threats;
- thirdly, the provision, development and use of the environment in the interests of the individual;
- fourthly, protection against various threats.

The study has revealed that the full-scale invasion of Russian troops into Ukraine has had a negative impact on the general state of psychological security of citizens, in particular, on such components of this indicator as morale and spiritual comfort. At the same time, it should be noted that the study does not cover all aspects of this issue; consequently, further prospects of the research will centre on studying complex integration approaches to the process of correcting the psychological security of the individual.

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